

TopBrain Segmentation Challenge for Whole Brain Vessel Anatomy: Version 2 with More Labels and Clinical Focus: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

TopBrain Segmentation Challenge for Whole Brain Vessel Anatomy: Version 2 with More Labels and Clinical Focus

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

TopBrain 2.0

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The second edition of the TopBrain challenge seeks to build on the momentum of its inaugural edition at MICCAI 2025, which introduced the first benchmark for multiclass segmentation of 48 landmark brain vessels for both arterial and venous systems in CT and MR angiography. The inaugural edition established a vibrant community of over 200 global registrants and 11 independent teams. Notably, two teams exceeded the performance of organizer-developed strong baselines, demonstrating both the community's capacity for innovation and the challenge's role as a catalyst for algorithmic development. Beyond the challenge itself, the original TopBrain dataset has also shown substantial research utility, surpassing 800 downloads on Zenodo and contributing to a podium-finish solution in the RSNA Aneurysm Detection Challenge.

In the updated TopBrain 2.0 version, we aim to improve the challenge in several key areas identified by community feedback and detailed post-challenge analysis. TopBrain 2.0 is specifically designed to bridge the gap between a testing-the-water baseline segmentation model and a clinically robust, diagnostically useful brain vessel analysis tool. To achieve this, we introduce five areas of improvement:

- 1) Expanded anatomy. We expand the list of anatomy labels to 55+, which now includes extradural/intradural segments of the internal carotid and vertebral arteries, the callosomarginal artery, and other venous structures (transverse/confluence sinuses). The added anatomies enrich the algorithm targets to essentially capture all the relevant vessels for clinical tasks such as locating aneurysms and occlusions, thus ensuring greater clinical applicability of the model.

2) Robustness to vascular pathology. To improve the clinical relevance of segmentation models, we will provide TopBrain annotations for images featuring labeled vessel lesions such as aneurysm and stenosis in both training and test data. While TopBrain 1.0 already had a subset of images with stenosis and occlusions, the lesion sites were not labeled. TopBrain 2.0 will now include vessel location labels for those occlusion/stenosis sites. We will also add aneurysm patients to the dataset and provide their TopBrain vessel annotations. Participants will be evaluated on their models' ability to maintain segmentation integrity in the presence of vessel lesions, a prerequisite for real-world downstream clinical tasks including lesion localization and treatment planning.

3) Tailored multiclass segmentation metrics. We will introduce more comprehensive metrics designed for many-class segmentation evaluations. A thorough analysis of the TopBrain 1.0 results revealed limitations in existing evaluation methods for multiclass vessel segmentation, particularly regarding fragmented class contaminations and failures to separate tortuous vessels that run in close parallel proximity to one another. To address this, we propose novel, specialized metrics to more accurately assess segmentation quality affected by class contamination and inter-class confusion.

4) New task for vessel-specific stenosis/occlusion classification. Other than the segmentation Task 1, we will introduce a Task 2 aimed at identifying vessel stenosis and grade its severity at over 15 predefined clinically significant vessel anatomies. All images in TopBrain 2.0 will include labels indicating the presence of stenosis and its severity grade (moderate, severe, occlusion) for the predefined vessel segments. Algorithm performance is evaluated for both stenosis grading accuracy and occlusion detection per vessel location. All Task 1 submissions are automatically evaluated for Task 2 via post-processing of segmentation outputs. However, participants are free to adopt diverse methods for Task 2, including but not limited to segmentation-based, detection-based, and hybrid multi-task approaches. This design enables us to compare how different methodologies perform at diagnosis of vessel occlusion and stenosis, a highly relevant downstream clinical task.

5) Targeted data curation. Analysis of the TopBrain 1.0 results indicated that thinner vessels and vessels that can be absent due to variants in anatomy are most in need of more training data. Thus, we will allocate annotation efforts towards these targeted vessel variants and challenging anatomies. Furthermore, the 2.0 version will curate data from new centers and new modalities (venography and 7T MRA) to push the limit of the data scope and generalizability.

Clinically, TopBrain has the potential to contribute to clinical workflow by automating the anatomy-aware localization of the vascular pathologies, thereby reducing the burden in vascular diagnostic workflow. To our knowledge, while there exist several commercial platforms for large vessel occlusion (LVO) triage, these tools cannot grade the stenosis severity and are not able to locate the occlusion for fine-grained anatomical locations. More importantly, there has never been a public benchmark for evaluating the diagnostic performance of LVO or stenosis detection algorithms. TopBrain identifies a more detailed anatomical context, which is particularly relevant to aneurysm treatment planning as the aneurysm location is a primary determinant of rupture risk and surgical approach. Furthermore, the inclusion of occlusion and stenosis labels in TopBrain can assist clinicians in stenosis diagnosis. Clinical guidelines generally define 70% and above stenosis as high-risk groups and use this threshold to guide management decisions. The location of the stenosis or occlusion also influences prognosis and intervention feasibility.

In summary, the updated TopBrain 2.0 challenge aims to improve on the initial results of TopBrain 1.0 with more labels and clinical focus. We propose to expand the anatomical and pathological labels, add tailored metrics and a clinically-oriented task, and incorporate diverse multi-modal data. TopBrain 2.0 hopes to establish a robust technical and translational benchmark for whole brain vessel segmentation and relevant downstream clinical tasks. We are highly enthusiastic about hosting TopBrain 2.0 at MICCAI and look forward to advancing this field with the research community.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Brain vessel segmentation, Multiclass anatomical segmentation, Brain vessel atlas, Multi-label ordinal classification, Large vessel occlusion, Vessel stenosis, Intracranial aneurysm

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

1. Anatomical Completeness. With the newly added extradural/intradural segments, anterior branches, and venous structures, TopBrain 2.0 increases the number of labels from 48 to 55+ and covers almost all the clinically relevant vascular anatomies of the brain.
2. Adversarial Robustness. TopBrain 2.0 focuses on vessel segmentation integrity and robustness against relevant vascular lesions like aneurysm, stenosis, and occlusion.
3. New multiclass metrics. We introduce tailored metrics that target class contamination and confusion, which are pertinent to evaluating multiclass brain vessel segmentation task.
4. New dataset and task for stenosis/occlusion-site and severity. We specifically evaluate for a clinically relevant task that classifies stenosis/occlusion based on fine-grained vessel anatomy and severity grade. To our knowledge, such a vessel-specific stenosis grading dataset is new.
5. Targeted data expansion. We prioritize data addition for "hard" cases where TopBrain 1.0 failed (confused vessels, anatomical variants) and with lesions.
6. New diverse modalities: To our knowledge, this will be the first public dataset with vessel and lesion annotations for venography modalities like MRV and CTV of the brain.
7. Unified multi-modal model. TopBrain 2.0 will combine all the modalities into one track (no more separate submissions for individual modalities), resulting in models that work across most common non-invasive neurovascular modalities: CTA, CTV, MRA (1.5, 3 and 7 Tesla), and MRV.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

1. Pre-operative planning for neurosurgical and endovascular procedures. Accurate segmentations of the brain vessel anatomy help surgeons characterize the vasculature and blood supply and plan the surgery such as the optimal access route and which vessels to preserve, bypass, or sacrifice.
2. Stenosis/occlusion localization with severity grades. Changes in the vessel caliber can be used to locate and grade stenosis/occlusion along the TopBrain vessel anatomy with its fine-grained anatomical resolution.

Automated and accurate anatomical localization of stenosis/occlusion can help in stroke and stenosis diagnosis and screening.

3. Aneurysm localization. TopBrain vessel anatomy and its segmentation masks can be combined with state-of-the-art aneurysm segmentation or detection tools to locate the parent vessel of the aneurysm.

4. The 3D whole brain vessel segmentation can also be combined with perfusion-based imaging to have both the temporal and anatomical information on blood flows. Anatomy-aware segmentation of the whole brain vessel can be merged with MR perfusion, CT perfusion of the same patient for a much more detailed understanding of the stroke condition and thus better treatment planning.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

We have coordinated with the organizers of three other related challenge/workshop: ISLES challenge 2026, TopAneu 2026 challenge, and SWITCH+ 2026 workshop, and we are happy to merge into a joint, comprehensive neurovascular event.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect 250+ registered participants and 20+ final submissions for the new iteration. The previous version had 200+ registered participants and resulted in 20+ final submissions across two tracks. With the new features and improvements introduced in the new version, and with the outreach from partnering neurovascular challenges, we anticipate continued interest and participation from the community.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

The challenge results of version 1.0 are in preparation will be uploaded as a pre-print for documentation prior to the commencement of the 2026 iteration. We will later combine the results from both years into a single benchmark paper for publication in a suitable journal.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

For the in-person event, we need projectors, microphones, loudspeakers, and a camera/videoconferencing system for hybrid participation.

The challenge will be hosted on grand-challenge.org. Participants use their own computing resources for the algorithm training and development. The recommended GPU memory requirement for high-resolution 3D data is at least 24GB. The organizers will use grand-challenge.org and local servers for the docker evaluation during the testing phase.

TASK 1: Task-1 Multiclass Segmentation of the Brain Vessels

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Task 1 aims to predict segmentation masks for over 55 classes of vessels across angiography (CTA/MRA) and venography (CTV/MRV) modalities. Segmentation performance will be evaluated for overlap, surface distance, connected components, valid neighbors, vessel presence detection, and class contamination metrics. The segmentation masks will also be automatically post-processed by our evaluation workflow to derive the stenosis/occlusion locations and grades, which will be jointly evaluated for Task 2 leaderboard.

While Task 1 is carried over from the inaugural edition, it has been enhanced with the following important updates:

1. More anatomy classes: Increased from 48 to 55+ classes to have finer anatomical granularities and larger scope
2. Robust to aneurysm presence: Dataset now includes images with aneurysms; algorithms are expected to be robust in vessel segmentation despite aneurysm presence
3. More image modalities: Inclusion of 7T MRA and venographic modalities
4. Unified modality model: A single submission track for all training modalities; no more separate submissions for individual modalities
5. New multiclass metrics: Introduction of metrics for inter-class contamination, a common error seen in TopBrain 1.0 results
6. Clinical translation evaluation for localization: Models will be assessed on their ability to facilitate downstream localization of stenosis and occlusions in tandem with Task 2

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multiclass segmentation, Brain vessel atlas, Anatomical segmentation, Inter-class contamination, Topology-aware segmentation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Same organizing team for both tasks.

[University of Zurich, Switzerland]

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Jonas Richiardi

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Kaiyuan Yang (kaiyuan.yang@uzh.ch) and Pengcheng Shi (shipc1220@gmail.com)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Clinicians are integral members of the organizing team and are responsible for:

Definition of Annotation Targets: Identifying clinically significant anatomical and pathological targets and defining the annotation protocol.

Quality Assurance & Verification: Manually reviewing and validating annotations to ensure high-fidelity ground truth.

Domain Expertise: Providing the clinical perspective and context to bridge the gap between algorithmic performance and clinical utility.

Clinical Impact Design: Designing downstream analysis and key objectives to assess how the proposed solutions could be integrated into diagnostic or surgical workflows.

Data Governance & Contribution: As data owners from various medical institutions, they oversee the curation, de-identification, and ethical sharing of the multi-center datasets.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

No URL available online for TopBrain 2.0 yet. Tentative: <https://topbrain-v2.grand-challenge.org/> Earlier TopBrain 1.0 URL: <https://topbrain2025.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants are allowed to use any other public datasets and private in-house data, or modify the supplied training data, provided that they disclose any additional or modified training datasets in their description of the submitted algorithm.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Members of the organizers' research groups can participate, and their results can be included in the publications and the leaderboard (marked as baseline algorithms). However, they are not eligible for awards.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Top three independent teams will be publicly named as shown on the grand-challenge leaderboard webpage, and given a small Swiss wooden toy and a booklet as souvenirs at the in-person challenge event. There will be no monetary awards given.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top performing submissions are announced at the in-person challenge event. However, the participating team can choose whether their results will be made public any time before the day of announcement. The top five teams will be invited to prepare a 5-minute presentation for the challenge session to present and discuss their methods.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All teams with reasonable submissions are invited to contribute to our challenge publication. Each team can have maximum three co-authors for the challenge paper. Additional authors from the submissions can be included upon request with justification according to the ICMJE authorship guidelines. Participating teams may publish their own results separately without any publication embargo.

To meet the requirement of co-authorship in the publication, a team must submit a write-up regarding their method description.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submission for evaluation will be done on the test datasets via submitted docker containers, i.e. type 2 submissions on Grand Challenge.

Along with the docker containers, each participating team is encouraged to submit a 1-page summary describing their methods and approaches. This summary is required for co-authorship in the final challenge journal paper.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Sanity-check phase: Consists of a 'toy' example docker submission phase. It is solely intended for teams to test whether their devised dockers work in the Grand Challenge cloud environment. Multiple submissions to this phase are allowed.

The test phases only allow one submission per team. Each team is given only one opportunity to upload their containers for the test set. In case of technical issues, we allow the participants to try again their docker submissions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Preliminary Schedule:

- Challenge website online: April 15, 2026
- Release of training data: July 05, 2026
- Submit to test phase: September 05 – September 15, 2026
- Contacting top performing teams and planning for the in-person session: Sep 04 – Oct 04, 2026
- in-person challenge event: Oct 04, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

All data are derived from studies that were approved by their local ethics committee. The data is anonymized (removal and anonymization of relevant patient information) in accordance with the IRB regulations. This includes de-facing and cropping procedures to ensure patient privacy in the image data, and the data do not contain any personal identifiers.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

Open use. Must provide the source. Use for commercial purposes requires permission of the data owner. (see <https://opendata.swiss/en/terms-of-use>)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Our challenge evaluation will be transparent to all participants. We will use a public GitHub repo to update and synchronize any changes to the evaluation code. The evaluation code for TopBrain 1.0 is at https://github.com/CoWBenchmark/TopBrain_Eval_Metrics/

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The submitted docker containers will be made publicly available with permissions from the participating teams. We highly encourage the participants to make their code public.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

We will not give monetary awards.

Only the main organizers and their local annotation team will have access to all test labels and the private test datasets.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research

- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,Diagnosis,Education

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Multiclass segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

A patient or healthy control undergoing a routine MRA/MRV/CTA/CTV scan, as an accurate whole brain vasculature characterization can be beneficial in many clinical applications, ranging from screening of patients being at a higher risk of stroke, to improving the clinical management of patients with cerebrovascular diseases.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort has both patients and healthy controls, with majority from patients of various hospital centers. The patients typically were admitted for stroke-related neurological disorder. Some patients were included for intracranial stenosis or intracranial aneurysm.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CT Angiography, MR Angiography, CT Venography, MR Venography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No contextual clinical information will be made available due to the requirement for anonymization.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No clinical information about the patient will be made available due to the requirement for anonymization.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain shown in CT or MR angiography or venography

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm targets for Task 1 segmentation are different anatomical vessel components of the whole brain/head. The vessel anatomies include:

External carotid artery region:

External carotid artery (ECA), left and right

Superficial temporal artery (STA), left and right

Maxillary artery (MaxA), left and right

Middle meningeal artery (MMA), left and right

Internal carotid artery region:

Extradural internal carotid artery (ICA), left and right

Intradural ICA, left and right

Ophthalmic artery (OA), left and right

Posterior communicating artery (Pcom), left and right

Anterior choroidal artery (AChA), left and right

Anterior cerebral artery region:

Anterior communicating artery (Acom)

A1 to A3 segments of anterior cerebral artery (ACA), right, and third-A2 variant

Callosomarginal artery (CMA), left and right

Middle cerebral artery region:

M1 to M3 segments of middle cerebral artery (MCA), left and right

Posterior circulation:

P1 to P4 segments of posterior cerebral artery (PCA), left and right

Basilar artery (BA)

Superior cerebellar artery (SCA), left and right

Anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA), left and right

V3 to V4 segments of vertebral artery (VA), left and right

Posterior inferior cerebellar artery (PICA), left and right

Veins:

Internal cerebral veins (ICVs)

Basal vein of Rosenthal (BVR), left and right

Vein of Galen (VoG)

Straight sinus (StS)

Superior sagittal sinus (SSS)

Confluence sinus (CS)

Transverse sinus (TS), left and right

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Data were typically acquired with CT and MRI systems from various manufacturers and scanner types during routine clinical practice. For MRI, this includes Siemens 1.5T and 3T systems. We also include data from public open datasets with 7T MRA modality. CTA systems include SIEMENS SOMATOM Definition Flash using Dual Energy (DE).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All images are obtained with acquisition parameters spanning within normal ranges used for clinical purposes. These differ between institutions providing datasets, but for example MRA is typically acquired with time-of-flight (TOF) angiography. For CTA, the voxel size was around 0.45 mm in the X-Y dimension, and around 0.7 mm in the Z dimension. For MRA, the voxel size was around 0.3 mm in the X-Y dimension, and around 0.6 mm in the Z dimension.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

New MRV and CTV data for both train and test sets will be extracted from University of Zurich (USZ), Switzerland.

MRA and CTA data with aneurysms are shared by the partnering TopAneu aneurysm challenge.

Additional stroke and stenosis patient data will be sampled from previous public datasets: TopCoW dataset [1], ISLES'24 dataset [2], and INSTED dataset [3].

MRA with 7 Tesla will be sampled from previous public dataset such as StudyForrest data[4].

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals operating CT and MRI systems in clinical routine.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in task-1 is a 3D angiographic imaging scan of a human brain in any of these modalities: CTA/MRA/CTV/MRV. The task is to segment the vessel anatomy of the whole head region. The relevant vessel components of the human brain are annotated voxel-wise, and different vessel segments are labeled with a different voxel value (see section Algorithm Target for the list). Both training and test cases are fully annotated.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Task 1 data is labeled with TopBrain vessel segmentation masks, and is a subset of Task 2 data.

Train set: 215 cases

By centers and modalities:

TopCoW CTA: 40

TopCoW MRA: 40

ISLES'24 CTA: 20

INSTED MRA: 20

USZ CTV: 20

USZ MRV: 20

StudyForrest 7T MRA: 5

TopAneu CTA with aneurysms: 25

TopAneu MRA with aneurysms: 25

Test set: 123 cases

By centers and modalities:

TopCoW CTA: 30

TopCoW MRA: 30

ISLES'24 CTA: 10

INSTED MRA: 10

USZ CTV: 10

USZ MRV: 10

StudyForrest 7T MRA: 3

TopAneu CTA with aneurysms: 10

TopAneu MRA with aneurysms: 10

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Train set: 50 (23%) annotated with TopBrain 1.0 labels

Test set: 40 (33%) annotated with TopBrain 1.0 labels

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

With more experience preparing a many-class segmentation dataset like in TopBrain 1.0, and thanks to the development of a good pre-labeling algorithm (~80% Dice), we are confident we can strike a balance between annotation quality and data size in the new edition. We expect to be able to scale up the training set to over 200 cases of high-quality annotations. The train-test proportion is at around 65-35 split. The test set of 120+ cases allow for a convincing evaluation covering sufficient variabilities of the anatomy.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Through data scaling experiments with TopBrain 1.0, we have found that some vessel classes have reached saturation in performance compared to other classes. Thus, we propose to have targeted data curation and sample more data for vessel classes in need.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The multiclass vessel annotations are new, including for previous public data.

For images, the venography and aneurysm cases will be newly released scans (130 = 38%), and majority of the test images are unseen, unpublished data (110 = 89%).

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

In TopBrain 2.0, we will use a human-in-the-loop approach to refine and upgrade our pre-labeling segmentation model iteratively, which is currently fairly accurate with ~80% Dice for TopBrain 1.0 labels. The predicted segmentation masks will be manually verified and corrected by an experienced human annotator. The cases that the annotator are uncertain will be flagged, and sent for further verification and approval by a senior neurosurgeon.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotation protocol on what and how to segment vessel components were discussed and agreed upon by the clinical experts. An experienced annotator was trained by a senior neurosurgeon on the annotation protocol.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The senior neurosurgeon who led the design of annotation protocol, trained the annotator, and verified the cases has over 10 years of professional experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The data were anonymized (removal and anonymization of relevant DICOM patient information). Additional de-facing and cropping procedures were performed to ensure patient privacy in the image data after converting the DICOM to NIfTI format. The defaced and cropped image includes only the brain region. All images are re-oriented to LPS+ orientation. Other than the defacing, the cropping to brain region, and re-orientation steps, no further preprocessing of the data is performed to keep the data as close to the clinical setting as possible.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The vessel can be slightly over-segmented or under-segmented in terms of tube thickness. MRA is prone to amplify changes in vessel caliber. CTA and CTV can be hard to segment veins or arteries of interest due to phase mix-up. The presence of aneurysms can disrupt the normal vessel anatomy and can be difficult to precisely outline the boundary between vessel and aneurysm.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

MR angiography may demonstrate incomplete venous suppression, while MR venography may exhibit incomplete arterial suppression.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

A comprehensive set of ten metrics will be used to evaluate Task 1 segmentation performance. These metrics are grouped into morphology-based, topology-based, anatomy-based, and class-contamination-based. They are all computed as class-average scores per image.

The morphology-based metrics:

1. Dice similarity coefficient (DSC)
2. Hausdorff Distance 95% Percentile (HD95)

The topology-based metrics:

3. Connected component (B0 number) error
4. Centerline Dice (cDice)

Anatomy-based metrics:

5. Number of invalid vessel neighbors
6. Detection F1 score of vessels that are thinner branches or can be absent due to variants (list of "side-road" vessels)

Class-contamination metrics:

7. Foreground contamination ratio
8. Number of sources for foreground contamination
9. Background contamination voxels
10. Number of sources for background contamination

Contamination is defined as any wrong class voxel.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Morphology-based metrics like Dice similarity coefficient and 95% percentile Hausdorff distance (HD95) are commonly used and thus allow for easier comparison with other studies. Some of the vessel components are smaller in diameter and volume, which are not best evaluated in overlap-based metrics like Dice scores as they are sensitive to small disagreement in voxels [5]. Thus, we introduce boundary-based metrics like Hausdorff distance to better evaluate vessel components with smaller size. HD95 is less affected by extreme outliers.

Topology-based metrics are important for brain vessel applications, especially the extent of brokenness and fragmentation. Centerline-Dice metric (cIDice) is suitable for evaluating voxel-wise overlap for tubular and curvilinear structures such as brain vessels [5].

Anatomy-based metrics ensure the segmentation outputs are anatomically correct. In particular, each vessel has a list of valid neighbor vessels and we penalize for any anatomically invalid classes.

Class-contamination metrics are a novelty of the 2.0 edition. We observed that with such a large number of possible classes, predicted masks can have cross-over and “stains” of wrong classes. Traditional metrics focus on class vs background evaluation, and lacks the capacity to highlight inter-class errors. Thus, we designed custom inter-class contamination metrics to capture such class-confusion problems in masks; and to raise awareness of common errors seen in TopBrain 1.0.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The ranking for the awards of the MICCAI event will be based on the leaderboards displayed on grand-challenge website, which rank the teams by sorting their performance on each metric. The leaderboard uses equal weights for each metric and ranks the submissions based on the mean rank position across all metrics.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For DCS, cIDice, and HD95, if the submitted method fails to produce a result on a test case, the metric for that test case will be set to its most penalizing value (0 for DSC and cIDice, dimension of the human head region for HD95).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The decision to utilize a mean rank across all metrics is driven by the multi-dimensional and cohort-based nature of the evaluation. This challenge evaluates performance across over 50 distinct anatomical locations, and the detection metrics are not available on a case level. A mean rank position of 10 comprehensive segmentation metrics helps identify the most clinically useful and robust algorithm. This ranking will be used to select the podium-finish teams that will be further evaluated with more external test data.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Post-challenge analysis will use bootstraps of the test set and analyze the ranking stability for bootstrapped average ranks. A bootstrap sample is obtained by sampling with replacement from the original test set, drawing the same number of observations as the original set.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Bootstrap samples of the test set (with the same number of cases as the original set) can be used to estimate confidence interval of the metrics of each team.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Our test cases come from various centers and have a range of modalities and underlying patient characteristics. We can stratify the analysis with sub-group analysis and comparison.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Bootstraps of the testset will be created, and each bootstrapped testset will be used to re-evaluate the algorithms and generate a new ranking. Then the bootstrapped ranks can be analyzed for ranking variability and stability.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Post challenge we can perform several statistical tests depending on the nature of the metric to compare closely-tied algorithms. For case-level metrics, Wilcoxon signed-rank test can be used to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between the two compared algorithms. For cohort-level detection metrics such as F1 score, statistical tests such as McNemar's Test can be used to compare algorithms for statistical significance.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Not applicable since our data are images with verified labels.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Scipy and Numpy with custom Python scripts.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We can perform ensembling of podium-finish top algorithms, and evaluate the ensemble prediction in the benchmark.

Following the conclusion of the public phase, the top-performing teams will have their models evaluated on an external private test set. This second phase is designed to evaluate the generalization capability of the algorithms. The results from this private evaluation represent a meaningful measure of a model's potential performance in a

real-world clinical environment.

For top teams that choose to train models with additional data, we strongly encourage them to also submit for benchmark a second model that is trained exclusively with the challenge dataset for the challenge paper.

TASK 2: Task-2 Vessel-Specific Occlusion/Stenosis Classification

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Task 2 aims to predict the presence and severity of stenosis for a subset of clinically relevant vessel classes. This task is formulated as a multi-label classification problem, where each image is associated with a set of labels indicating the presence of stenosis and its severity grade at around 15 predefined high-priority vessel locations. The stenosis severity grades are divided into four ordinal grades based on the extent of narrowing: absent (0-49% narrowing), moderate (50-69% narrowing), severe (70-99% narrowing), and occlusion (100% narrowing).

While stenosis or occlusion can theoretically occur at any point along the vascular tree, TopBrain 2.0 intentionally targets the most clinically relevant sites. Around 15 high-priority vessel anatomies will be included:

- Intradural internal carotid artery (ICA), left and right
- Extradural ICA, left and right
- Anterior cerebral artery (ACA), left and right
- M1 segment of middle cerebral artery (MCA), left and right
- Intradural (V4) segment of vertebral artery (VA), left and right
- P1 to P2 segments of posterior cerebral artery (PCA), left and right
- Basilar artery (BA)
- Ophthalmic artery (OA), left and right
- Superior sagittal sinus (SSS)
- Straight sinus (StS)
- Transverse sinus (TS), left and right
- Deep veins, including the vein of Galen and basal veins

Algorithm performance will be evaluated on two aspects: F1 score of occlusion detection and mean absolute error (MAE) of stenosis grade for each relevant vessel location class. This set of metrics mirrors how a clinician looks at an image: first they find the lesion (detection), then they characterize its severity (grading).

To our knowledge, while there exist several commercial platforms for large vessel occlusion (LVO) triage, these tools cannot grade the stenosis severity and are not able to locate the occlusion for fine-grained anatomical locations. More importantly, there has never been a public benchmark for evaluating the diagnostic performance of LVO or stenosis detection algorithms. Task 2 of TopBrain 2.0 addresses these gaps by establishing the first transparent, public benchmark for fine-grained stenosis localization and grading analysis. By evaluating models on 15+ specific anatomical sites, we challenge the community to move beyond simple triage toward a clinically robust, automated diagnostic tool that meets the clinical needs.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multilabel classification, Large vessel occlusion (LVO), Medium vessel occlusion (MeVO), Moderate-to-sever stenosis

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Same organizing team for both tasks.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Same as Task 1

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Same as Task 1

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Same as Task 1

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Same as Task 1

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Same as Task 1

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Same as Task 1

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Same as Task 1

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Same as Task 1

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Same as Task 1

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Same as Task 1

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Same as Task 1

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Same as Task 1

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to

compute challenge results.

Same as Task 1

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Same as Task 1

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Same as Task 1

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

Same as Task 1

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Same as Task 1

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Same as Task 1

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Same as Task 1

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,Diagnosis,Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction

- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Multi-label ordinal classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 1

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Same as Task 1

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Same as Task 1

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Same as Task 1

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Same as Task 1

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

While stenosis or occlusion can theoretically occur at any point along the vascular tree, TopBrain 2.0 intentionally targets the most clinically relevant sites. Around 15 high-priority vessel anatomies will be included for stenosis targets:

- Intradural internal carotid artery (ICA), left and right
- Extradural ICA, left and right
- Anterior cerebral artery (ACA), left and right
- M1 segment of middle cerebral artery (MCA), left and right
- Intradural (V4) segment of vertebral artery (VA), left and right
- P1 to P2 segments of posterior cerebral artery (PCA), left and right
- Basilar artery (BA)
- Ophthalmic artery (OA), left and right
- Superior sagittal sinus (SSS)
- Straight sinus (StS)
- Transverse sinus (TS), left and right
- Deep veins, including the vein of Galen and basal veins

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Precision,Sensitivity,Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Same as Task 1

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Same as Task 1

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Same as Task 1

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Same as Task 1

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in task-2 is a 3D angiographic imaging scan of a human brain in any of these modalities: CTA/MRA/CTV/MRV. The task is to classify the stenosis grade for specified vessel segments (see section Algorithm Target for the list). The stenosis label are ordinal grades from absent, moderate, severe, to occlusion. Both training and test cases are fully annotated.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Task 2 data is labeled with stenosis classification, and is a superset of Task 1 data.

Train set: 315 cases

By centers and modalities:

TopCoW CTA: 70

TopCoW MRA: 70

ISLES'24 CTA: 30

INSTED MRA: 30

USZ CTV: 30

USZ MRV: 30

StudyForrest 7T MRA: 5

TopAneu CTA with aneurysms: 25

TopAneu MRA with aneurysms: 25

Test set: 183 cases

By centers and modalities:

TopCoW CTA: 40

TopCoW MRA: 40

ISLES'24 CTA: 20

INSTED MRA: 20

USZ CTV: 20

USZ MRV: 20

StudyForrest 7T MRA: 3

TopAneu CTA with aneurysms: 10

TopAneu MRA with aneurysms: 10

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Train set: ~120 (38%) annotated with stenosis or occlusion in the form of metadata text or masks

Test set: ~80 (44%) partially annotated like in train set

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Task 2 label is lighter to obtain compared to Task 1. Thus, we estimate we can have better scalability in data size for Task 2 with over 300 cases for train and 180 cases for test. The train-test proportion is around 65-35 split, with sufficient test images to cover all the stenosis sites for a fair evaluation.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The dataset will be specifically curated to ensure sufficient representation of stenosis/occlusion on the included anatomical vessel locations. We will implement a stratified sampling approach to guarantee that each of the anatomical vessel locations (left and right together) contains at least three positive samples in both training and test sets. By ensuring a minimum number of occurrences per location, we provide a baseline for cross-validation and ensure that the winning models demonstrate generalized diagnostic capability across the entire vascular tree.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The stenosis and occlusion classification labels are new, including for previous public data. The venography and aneurysm cases will be newly released images (170 = 34%), and majority of the test images are unseen, unpublished data (160 = 87%).

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The stenosis and occlusion will be manually labeled by a member of our clinical experts for the anatomical vessel location name and stenosis severity.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

All annotators were given a comprehensive review of our specified vessel anatomical locations for stenosis detection and grading. The stenosis and occlusion site definition will be based on the scheme defined in ISLES'24 [2] and the WASID criteria [6].

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The clinicians who label the stenosis are senior neurosurgeons and neurologists.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as Task 1

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

MRA might amplify the effect of stenosis in vessels. CTA/CTV show calcified vessels which can interfere with stenosis grading.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The bones in CTA/CTV may interfere with stenosis diagnosis for vessels near or surrounded by bones.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Two metrics used for the multi-label ordinal classification task:

Per-vessel mean absolute error (MAE) of stenosis grade

Per-vessel occlusion detection F1 score

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

F1 is the harmonic mean of recall and precision. It can handle class imbalance of occlusion prevalence in certain vessel locations. Occlusion is also the most severe grade of the stenosis, so we want to specifically evaluate for the detection performance of occlusion. Mean absolute error is used to capture how wrong the classification is at severity grading. MAE of grades can be coupled with occlusion detection to indicate clinically useful workflow. Furthermore, we report the metrics per-vessel since the focus of our challenge is to evaluate stenosis algorithms

for each fine-grained anatomical location.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Same as Task 1

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the submitted method fails to produce a result on a test case, the evaluation will return an error and abort.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The decision to utilize a mean rank across all metrics is driven by the cohort-based nature of the evaluation. This challenge evaluates performance across over 15 distinct anatomical locations, and the detection metrics are not available on a case level. A mean rank of grade MAE and occlusion F1 helps identify the most clinically useful and robust algorithm. This ranking will be used to select the podium-finish teams that will be further evaluated with more external test data.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Same as Task 1

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Same as Task 1

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Same as Task 1

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We can perform ensembling of podium-finish top algorithms, and evaluate the ensemble prediction in the benchmark.

Following the conclusion of the public phase, the top-performing teams will have their models evaluated on an external private test set. This second phase is designed to evaluate the generalization capability of the algorithms. The results from this private evaluation represent a meaningful measure of a model's potential performance in a real-world clinical environment.

We will perform inter-rater agreement analysis on the annotations.

For top teams that choose to train models with additional data, we strongly encourage them to also submit for benchmark a second model that is trained exclusively with the challenge dataset for the challenge paper.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

[1] Yang, K., Musio, F., Ma, Y., Juchler, N., Paetzold, J. C., Al-Maskari, R., ... & Menze, B. (2023). TopCoW: Benchmarking Topology-Aware Anatomical Segmentation of the Circle of Willis (CoW) for CTA and MRA. arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.17670.

[2] Riedel, E. O., de la Rosa, E., Baran, T. A., Petzsche, M. H., Baazaoui, H., Yang, K., ... & Kirschke, J. S. (2024). ISLES 2024: The first longitudinal multimodal multi-center real-world dataset in (sub-) acute stroke. arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.11142.

[3] INSTED: Intracranial Aneurysm and Intracranial Artery Stenosis Detection and Segmentation Challenge: <https://zenodo.org/records/10990482>

[4] StudyForrest: <https://studyforrest.org/access.html>

[5] Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P., Tizabi, M. D., Buettner, F., Christodoulou, E., ... & Jäger, P. F. (2024). Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nature methods*, 21(2), 195-212.

[6] Samuels, O. B., Joseph, G. J., Lynn, M. J., Smith, H. A., & Chimowitz, M. I. (2000). A standardized method for measuring intracranial arterial stenosis. *American journal of neuroradiology*, 21(4), 643-646.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A